

PARENT'S STRESS INVENTORY: A TOOL DEVELOPMENT

Michelle Abella-Cellona, RPsy, PhD

*Psychology Area, Cebu Institute of Technology-University, Cebu City, Cebu,
Philippines*

MindProCebu Psychological Services, Cebu City, Cebu, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10825314>

ABSTRACT

This study introduces the Stress Inventory, an assessment tool designed specifically to evaluate parental stress. The inventory utilizes a 4-point Likert scale to gauge the severity of stress with 37 statements. Every statement explores the presence of stress manifestations among parents throughout the previous 14 days. The research involved 697 parents from Cebu City, utilizing the inventory to assess stress status. The analysis indicated that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each statement remained within the acceptable range, affirming the reliability of the inventory in measuring parental stress level. The utilization of Cronbach's alpha scores to evaluate each statement within the inventory displayed a remarkable level of reliability and internal consistency. These scores fell within the acceptable range, underscoring a high level of coherence and interconnectedness among the queries assessing parental stress. Hence, these robust metrics provide a solid foundation for accurately gauging and comprehending the intricate experiences of stress encountered by parents. Conclusively, the Stress Inventory emerges as a dependable and valid tool for comprehensively evaluating the range of stress experienced by parents, providing a valuable instrument for both clinical and research purposes.

Keywords: *Parental stress, Stress inventory, Cronbach's alpha, Emotional manifestations, Cognitive manifestations, Behavioral manifestations, Physiological manifestations*

INTRODUCTION

Parental stress significantly influences family dynamics and the overall well-being of children. Stress has become increasingly prevalent among parents today, as evidenced by various articles and research studies. The challenges of achieving a work-life balance (Gragano, et al. 2020), contribute significantly to parental stress, often arising from conflicting demands between work and family responsibilities. Additionally, financial pressures, including job instability and rising living costs, have been linked to heightened stress levels among parents (Friedline, et al. 2021). Parenting challenges such as concerns about raising children in a competitive environment, disciplinary issues, and meeting societal expectations also contribute to parental stress. Furthermore, the pervasive influence of technology and social media introduces additional stressors by fostering comparisons, concerns about children's screen time, and unrealistic parenting standards portrayed online. Moreover, as discussed in a study by Adams et al. (2021), the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly amplified parental stress due to health concerns, disruptions in routines, remote learning challenges, and increased caregiving responsibilities.

Recognizing this crucial interplay and all other concerns raised by the clients in the researcher's psychological clinic, this Inventory as a dedicated tool to comprehensively evaluate and understand the levels of stress of parents is designed.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the reliability and validity of the newly developed stress inventory in assessing stress among parents. Specifically, it sought answers of the following questions:

1. What is the level of reliability of the stress inventory in measuring the stress manifestations of parents in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive,
 - 1.2. emotional,
 - 1.3. behavioral, and
 - 1.4. physiological?
2. What recommendation may be forwarded for the improvement of the mental health of parents particularly in handling stress.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants of this study were the parents of the enrolled students at the two HEIs of Cebu City. They consist of 192 males (27.54%) and 505 females (72.46%) with a mean age of 41.19. It was conducted on the day the respective institutions held a parents' workshop on mental health. The workshop was facilitated by a Registered

Psychologist and was assisted by guidance counselors, principals, teachers, psychometricians, and psychology interns.

Procedure

The HEIs where the study was conducted, respectively, had workshops about mental health for their institutions. They were held on different dates. During the registration and ushering of the participants, the tool and instructions were given to them. They were informed of the option of wanting to answer the survey or not.

Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology student interns were strategically assigned within the venue to assist the participants with their concerns or clarifications.

The researcher then prepared the inventory to identify the level of stress of the research participants. An informed consent form was stated at the bottom page of the instrument for the research participants to sign should they agree to participate in the research conducted. An appointment was set with the guidance counselors of the two participating HEIs of Cebu City. The questionnaires were given to each department for review and reproduction.

Before the start of the workshop, a one-hour ushering-in activity was done, where participants were given the instruments and instructions. Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology interns were strategically situated in the venue to assist at least 5-7 parents, making sure that someone would answer their questions or clarifications. Once the questionnaires were given to them, the consent forms were cut off and gathered, but they were placed separately to further keep the answers random and confidential.

All the questionnaires were then collated into one population. Each statement of the inventory and its corresponding answers were then tallied to produce their frequency and percentage in the population. The researcher then clustered the statements into tables that showed similarities in nature and labeled it with its respective theme.

Instrument

The Stress Inventory is a self-report tool used to gauge levels of stress of parents. A 4-point anchored scale is used to rate the frequency of each manifestation within a fourteen-day timeframe with 0 for Not at all, 1 for Less than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (1-6 days), 2 for More than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (7-13 days), and 3 for Always (Everyday). These constructs assessed various manifestations such as cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological.

Scoring

Each statement in the inventory is scored based on how strongly the manifestations were felt during a specific period. A score of 0 indicates that the manifestations were not felt at all, while a score of 3 indicates that they were felt

every day. Total scores were summed up to get the mean score and were classified as either No, Low, Moderate, and High.

Content Validity of the Instrument

In the development of the inventory, the crucial role of content validity was highlighted, emphasizing its necessity for tests to comprehensively cover the constructs they are designed to assess. This entails a detailed verification process, often requiring consensus among experts for thorough evaluation (Nikolopoulou, 2023). To ensure the assessment tool's relevance, clarity, and comprehensive coverage of the intended construct, an initial review of the items was conducted by experts in psychology, parenting, and psychometrics. Moreover, the qualitative phase of the study utilized a content analysis approach, incorporating semi-structured, in-depth interviews with three psychologists and two psychometrists, all with significant experience in working with parents within their psychological practice. This expert feedback proved instrumental in refining the inventory, guiding the revision, addition, and deletion of items to enhance the instrument's content validity. Such a process was pivotal in ensuring that the inventory accurately reflects the domain of depression among parents, thus making it a valid tool for assessing this specific psychological construct.

Pilot Testing

To ensure the questionnaire really captures what it's meant to, we tested a first version with a small group of 10 parents, split evenly between men and women. This test helped us see if the questions were clear and if the questionnaire was easy to use.

Data Treatment

To evaluate the internal consistency or reliability of the questionnaire items, Cronbach's alpha was employed. This method involves assessing the shared variance or covariance among the items within the instrument compared to the total variance observed. The underlying principle is that a higher covariance among the items, relative to the overall variance, signifies a reliable instrument. Essentially, Cronbach's alpha calculates the average of all possible split-half reliabilities, providing a standardized measure of agreement between the items on a scale from 0 to 1. Higher Cronbach's alpha values suggest a higher level of agreement among the items, reflecting consistency in participants' responses across a set of questions. This consistency is crucial for the development and evaluation of new survey instruments. A Cronbach's alpha threshold of 0.7 was established as a benchmark for sufficient consistency, indicating that the measure is reliable. While values around 0.7 are considered minimally acceptable, they are not ideal; conversely, excessively high values may suggest redundancy among the questions.

RESULTS

In the pursuit of assessing the reliability of each statement within the inventory, the study explored the application of Cronbach's alpha as a key metric. Cronbach's alpha serves as a fundamental tool in evaluating the internal consistency or reliability of the measurement scale employed within the research framework (Goforth, 2015). This statistical method aids in gauging the extent of interrelatedness among the items in the assessment tool, shedding light on how consistently these items measure the same construct. By employing Cronbach's alpha, the investigation aimed to ascertain the reliability of each statement within the stress inventory concerning stress as experienced by parents. This analysis provided crucial insights into the strength and consistency of the inventory's measurements, ensuring a thorough evaluation of the various facets of stress prevalent among the participants (Taber, 2018).

Stress Inventory

Table 1.1 Cognitive Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.915
95% CI lower bound	0.905
95% CI upper bound	0.924
Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped Cronbach's α
S1	0.908
S3	0.908
S4	0.907
S6	0.905
S7	0.904
S8	0.905
S9	0.912
S16	0.905
S18	0.909
S26	0.904
S34	0.907

Table 1.1 displays key reliability statistics that were calculated using individual item analysis. A strong estimate of internal consistency is revealed by the scale reliability statistics, measured by Cronbach's α , which produce a point estimate of 0.915 with a 95% confidence interval between 0.905 and 0.924. Since none of the individual items considerably increases the overall reliability when eliminated, the values, which range from 0.904 to 0.912, confirm the long-term reliability of the inventory's internal consistency. Among the items in this domain of stress included in the instrument were: S1 "I worry about the tasks/job I am currently doing", S7 "I am bothered with my family situation, and S34 "I would like to make changes in my life but do not know how." These statements were considered to be included in the instrument as stress can cause worry and affect decision-making skills (Eske, 2019; Simon et al., 2021).

Collectively, these results highlight the excellent degree of internal consistency and reliability displayed by the scale and each of its items within the assessment tool for assessing cognitive manifestation of stress among parents.

Table 1.2 Emotional Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.895
95% CI lower bound	0.883
95% CI upper bound	0.906

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
S2	0.885
S5	0.880
S10	0.884
S12	0.896
S15	0.884
S20	0.885
S25	0.881
S29	0.883
S37	0.884
S21	0.885

Table 1.2 illustrates vital reliability statistics obtained from a frequentist analysis, encompassing both the scale and individual item evaluations. In terms of the scale reliability statistics, Cronbach's α demonstrates a robust internal consistency, yielding a

point estimate of 0.895, categorized as 'GOOD,' with a 95% confidence interval between 0.883 and 0.906. Additionally, the individual item reliability statistics showcase Cronbach's α values if each respective item were to be excluded from the scale. These values, ranging from 0.880 to 0.896, affirm the strong internal consistency of the inventory. Notably, the removal of any particular statement does not significantly impair the overall reliability, so confirming the instrument's reliability and consistency in evaluating parents' emotional manifestation of stress.

It's important to note that these calculations include assessments of sample statements from the instrument, such as Statement 2 "I feel that I have too much responsibility", Statement 15 "I feel that I carry other people's problems", and Statement 29 "I feel exhausted when deadlines are piled up". The inclusion of these statements illustrates the range of concerns addressed by the instrument as problems, workload, and the demand to perform their responsibilities add to their stress (Leitch et al., 2019). Moreover, it reinforces its comprehensive nature.

Table 1.3 Behavioral Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.919
95% CI lower bound	0.910
95% CI upper bound	0.927

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
S11	0.912
S13	0.915
S14	0.910
S17	0.912
S19	0.912
S22	0.914
S23	0.921
S24	0.911
S27	0.913
S28	0.912
S31	0.916
S33	0.913
S35	0.911
S36	0.911

Table 1.3 shows the key reliability metrics from a frequentist analysis which include scale and item-level inventory evaluations. With respect to the reliability statistics of the scale, Cronbach's α indicates an exceptional degree of internal consistency, with a point estimate of 0.919, classified as 'Excellent,' and a 95% confidence interval spanning from 0.910 to 0.927. Additionally, the Cronbach's α values for each individual item on the scale would be displayed in the individual item dependability data. The assessment tool's remarkable internal consistency and dependability are further confirmed by these numbers, which constantly fall between 0.910 and 0.921. Remarkably, the absence of any specific item does not considerably impair the overall reliability, highlighting the strength and consistency of the inventory in evaluating the behavioral manifestation of stress among parents.

Incorporating an examination of specific sample statements from the instrument, such as Statement 13 "I handle most things alone with little support from my family and/or friends", Statement 27 "I tend to lash out (yell/shout at) people when my tasks are overwhelming", and Statement 35 "I commit more mistakes when tasks are overwhelming", enriches our understanding of the inventory's scope. These statements are illustrative of the diverse concerns and stressors the instrument seeks to capture, underscoring its comprehensiveness in evaluating the behavioral manifestations of stress among parents.

Table 1.4 Physiological Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.709
95% CI lower bound	0.662
95% CI upper bound	0.750

Note: Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

In Table 1.4, we have information about how reliable the statements are in showing physiological manifestations, based on the Cronbach's alpha scale. In this case, the point estimate is 0.709, marked as 'Acceptable' which means these statements together are somewhat consistent in measuring the physiological reactions. Overall, these statements show an acceptable level of consistency in assessing the physiological manifestation of stress in parents.

The two items of this domain are: Statement 30 "I experience cold flashes/sweating/increased heart rate when questioned about unfinished tasks" and Statement 32 "When tasks are piled up, I can feel my head aches", which are some indicators of stress found in some studies (Zamkah et al., 2020).

DISCUSSION

The data presented across Tables 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4 offer a detailed insight into the reliability of a stress inventory aimed at measuring various manifestations of stress among parents. The Cronbach's alpha values reported in Tables 1.1 (0.915), 1.2 (0.895), and 1.3 (0.919) for cognitive, emotional, and behavioral stress manifestations, respectively, demonstrate an exceptional degree of internal consistency. These values, well within the excellent to good range, underscore the inventory's capability to provide reliable assessments across these dimensions of parental stress. Notably, the stability of these values, even with the hypothetical removal of individual items, attests to the careful construction of the inventory, ensuring that no single item disproportionately affects the overall reliability.

The high reliability indices suggest that the inventory can serve as a robust tool in both clinical and research settings, facilitating the nuanced assessment of stress's cognitive, emotional, and behavioral impacts on parents. This precision allows for targeted interventions and supports the development of tailored strategies to address specific stress facets effectively.

However, Table 1.4 reveals a slightly different scenario for the physiological manifestation of stress, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.709. While this value is deemed 'Acceptable' and indicates a reasonable level of internal consistency, it falls short of the higher reliability marks seen in the other domains. This discrepancy highlights a potential area for refinement within the inventory, suggesting that the physiological stress items may require further development or revision to achieve the same level of reliability as the other sections. This could involve adding new items, revising existing ones, or conducting additional research to better capture the physiological responses associated with parental stress.

Overall, the findings across these tables collectively affirm the stress inventory's utility in capturing a comprehensive picture of parental stress. Yet, they also signal the need for continuous improvement, particularly in the physiological domain, to enhance the tool's effectiveness in all stress manifestations. This holistic approach to measuring parental stress not only facilitates a deeper understanding of its multifaceted nature but also paves the way for more effective interventions tailored to the specific needs of parents.

Conclusions

The study underscores the robustness and applicability of the developed inventory in comprehensively evaluating and assessing the level of stress among parents. The reliability analysis, indicated by Cronbach's α , revealed consistently high internal consistency across different domains, signifying the reliability of this tool in measuring cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological manifestations of stress. Moreover, the observed stability of the scale and minimal impact on reliability when individual items were dropped further supports its integrity and usefulness in evaluating the

manifestations. This tool exhibits promising potential for both research and clinical applications, offering a reliable, comprehensive, and internally consistent means to evaluate diverse manifestations of stress. Its multifaceted nature aligns with the growing recognition of the need for a dimensional approach, which could greatly contribute to more nuanced understandings of various psychological conditions and inform tailored intervention strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and strengths of the study on the development and validation of a stress inventory for parents, the following recommendations are made:

1. Researchers are encouraged to use this inventory to delve deeper into the complexities of parental stress. Given its reliability and thorough coverage, it serves as an excellent resource for investigating how stress varies among different parenting scenarios.
2. Healthcare providers such as psychologists, counselors, and social workers assisting parents should utilize this inventory for assessing needs and crafting intervention plans. Its capability to pinpoint distinct areas of stress enables the development of customized support and therapeutic strategies.
3. While the inventory has shown reliability, further validation studies should be conducted across diverse cultural and socio-economic groups to ensure its applicability and sensitivity to different parenting experiences globally.
4. Training programs for healthcare providers, educators, and social service professionals should include the use of this inventory to enhance their understanding of parental stress and improve support services for families.
5. Policymakers in the community and program developers should utilize insights from the inventory to design and implement support systems, policies, and programs aimed at reducing parental stress and promoting family well-being.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All applicable institutional guidelines where the study was conducted were followed. The participants were informed of their freedom to answer the survey instrument. All who had submitted their answers had written informed consent.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her heartfelt gratitude to the distinguished experts, psychologists, psychometrist, and statistician who have contributed immensely to this research endeavor. Their insights, expertise, and unwavering support have been pivotal in shaping the development and validation of the stress inventory for parents.

To the principals of the respective institutions for allowing the study to be conducted. Their expression of willingness and enthusiasm to also help and understand the parents of their institutions was inspiring and motivating.

To the guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology interns who were present in assisting the researcher and participants when the study was being held. Their attentiveness to the participants' needs during the time was helpful not only to them, but also to the researcher.

To the MindProCebu Psychological Services research group, their time, efforts in collating with the data gathered, and thoughts of the study made this endeavor more insightful.

REFERENCES

- Adams, E. L., Smith, D., Caccavale, L. J., & Bean, M. K. (2021). Parents Are Stressed! Patterns of Parent Stress Across COVID-19. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 12, 626456. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.626456>
- Eske, J. Healthdirect Australia. (2019). Irritability and feeling on edge. Healthdirect. <https://www.healthdirect.gov.au/irritability-and-feeling-on-edge>.
- Friedline, T., Chen, Z., & Morrow, S. (2021). Families' Financial Stress & Well-Being: The Importance of the Economy and Economic Environments. *Journal of family and economic issues*, 42(Suppl 1), 34–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-020-09694-9>
- Goforth, C. (2015) Using and Interpreting Cronbach's Alpha. University of Virginia Library. Retrieved from: <https://library.virginia.edu/data/articles/using-and-interpreting-cronbachs-alpha>
- Gragnano, A., Simbula, S., & Miglioretti, M. (2020). Work-Life Balance: Weighing the Importance of Work-Family and Work-Health Balance. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(3), 907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030907>
- Leitch, S., Sciberras, E., Post, B., Gerner, B., Rinehart, N., Nicholson, J. M., & Evans, S. (2019) Experience of stress in parents of children with ADHD: A qualitative study, *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 14:1, DOI: 10.1080/17482631.2019.1690091
- Simon, L., Jiryis, T., & Admon, R. (2021). Now or Later? Stress-Induced Increase and Decrease in Choice Impulsivity Are Both Associated with Elevated Affective and Endocrine Responses. *Brain Sciences*, 11(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11091148>
- Taber, K.S. (2018) The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Res Sci Educ* 48, 1273–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>

Zamkah, A., Hui, T., Andrews, S., Dey, N., Shi, F., Sherratt, R.S. (2020). Identification of Suitable Biomarkers for Stress and Emotion Detection for Future Personal Affective Wearable Sensors. *Biosensors* 2020, 10 (4), p. 40.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/bios10040040>